

SOCIAL SCIENCES

THE EVALUATION OF RESEARCH CAPACITY IN GEORGIAN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS - CHALLENGES AND OPPORTUNITIES

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Abstract

This research represents a study and analysis performed by a group of researchers on an important problem, which is very acute in the modern Georgian scientific society. Besides, it is already 17 years that Georgia has been a participant country in the Bologna process, there are a number of issues in the education system, which are quite important for the country's sustainable development. It must be noted that the outflow of intellectual resources, the difficulties existing in science still remain a challenge for the country. Herewith, the mechanisms for the support of the academic personnel working at universities is also a problem (resources: time, finances, professional development, etc.), to help them spend major time on research, create a valuable product and contribute to the development of the country.

The research describes the challenges and problems faced by academic personnel, and the perspectives of further development.

Keywords: University, Academic personnel, Research capacity, challenges and opportunities.

Introduction

The Georgian educational reform has been in progress for several years already. In 2005 Georgia signed the Berger Communiqué, and since that, we have joined the Bologna Process (Joint Declaration of the European Ministers of Education convened in Bologna June, 1999), (Berger Summit, 2005) therefore a number of activities have been implemented in the country in terms of higher education, which assisted it in holding honourable position on the way to the EU. Though, there are issues, which still remain as challenges. Among them is the promotion of the scientists' research activities, which is very important for the development of the country.

After the dissolution of the Soviet Union, the outflow of intellectual resources from the country began. A number of famous scientists from various fundamental fields have left Georgia and today they work abroad. Therefore, the country has been left without significant competence, which is very important for raising future generations.

Based on the reality existing in Georgia, researchers have lacked relevant conditions at the end of the last century and are still lacking them. Students and young scientists with outstanding talent take their path to the West.

The following problems have been identified by a group of researchers:

✓ Outflow of intellectual resources, a great number of distinguished scientists have left the country;

✓ There are no appropriate approaches at the Master's and Doctoral levels in order to maintain the quality of research;

✓ The academic personnel working at universities do not have appropriate conditions (resources: time, finances, professional development) in order to spend significant time on research, also, to work with Master's and Doctoral students with appropriate workload;

✓ The internal and external quality control mechanisms are not fully effective in order to provide academic personnel with maximum support from the university.

Based on all the above-mentioned, the problems raised in the paper are quite topical and there are few studies in Georgian scientific space in this direction. Therefore, it will have substantial importance for the identification of problems and for finding the ways of their solution, also, for understanding the challenges that Georgia is going to face in the future, on the path to the EU and the opportunities existing for the change of the country's reality in terms of the studies.

The goal of the study is to identify and demonstrate the challenges and problems faced by researchers today, also, to evaluate the opportunities and the potential of the country in terms of the studies, after studying the existing reality.

Herewith, certain recommendations have been prepared, and we think that they will promote the development of a strong scientific society on the levels of educational institutions and the country.

Research objectives:

✓ Assessment of the conditions existing within the university space, among them, their problems, challenges and opportunities in terms of promotion and development of research;

✓ Review of successful international practice (including the Post-Soviet Union countries);

✓ Determination of approaches, that would be useful for the educational system of Georgia for promoting research;

✓ Establishment of communication channels for providing information on the opportunities for participation in international research projects at universities.

Research questions

✓ To what extent do the regulations existing in the country express the declared state policy?

✓ To what extent have the approaches determined by the state turned into reality?

✓ What research potential does a higher educational space have and what are the main challenges faced by Georgian researchers?

Data collection methodology:

✓ The situation and regulations existing in terms of research: data collection and analysis;

✓ University surveys: drawing up questionnaires and studying the events held for promoting scientists at private and public universities (8 private /public universities: among them – 4 universities in Tbilisi and 4 universities in regions);

✓ Interviews with researchers and the persons working in the educational space.

State policy existing in Georgia in terms of the development of science

As it has already been noted, since 2005, i.e., the time when Georgia joined the Bologna Process, ensuring the quality of education has become part of the agenda. Afterward, the changes were made to the Law of Georgia On Higher Education, Law of Georgia On Quality Enhancement, (Parliament, 2010) ‘‘National Qualifications Framework’’ and other important documents were adopted, which should promote harmonization on the road to Europe. After that, as a consequence of the meetings between the representatives of the Bologna Process states, the reports on the implemented activities were submitted and the future strategic goals were determined, setting respective plans. In order to ensure the mentioned approaches, the European Standards Guidebook (ESG) – the Quality Assurance Standards and Guiding Principles of the European Higher Education Space - ESG 2015 (ESG სტანდარტების სახელმძღვანელო) were developed for participant countries in 2015.

Therefore, new authorization standards were approved by the Ministry of Education and Science of Georgia, according to Annex №3 to the Order 07/N of January 31, 2018, in order to promote the development of the quality of education at higher education institutions and ensure a student-oriented environment. (the ‘‘approval of regulation of Authorization of educational institutions and its fees; No07/N , 31 January 2018 Tbilisi)

According to the 6th authorization standard (research, development and/or other creative activities),

each higher education institution, considering the type and the field(s), shall take care of the reinforcement of its own research function, ensure the creation of the conditions promoting research and enhancement of the quality of research activities and its internationalization.

The promotion of research activities is one of the main priorities of the Ministry of Education and Science of Georgia. It creates the opportunity for higher education institutions in terms of expanding activities in different directions.

The deepening of the research potential is one of the main components in the strategies of development of the higher education institutions existing in the country, (websites: Akaki Tsereteli State University; Batumi Shota Rustaveli State University; Tbilisi State Medical University, (<https://www.atsu.edu.ge>, n.d.) (<https://www.bsu.edu.ge>, n.d.) (<https://tsmu.edu/ts>, n.d.), 2023) for this purpose, it is necessary to create a relevant, transparent environment for research and corresponding initiatives. In particular, promote the revealing of young researchers and their development, participation of students/personnel in scientific projects, cooperation with both – local and partner organizations, development of research infrastructure, etc.

However, it must be noted that in the applicable legal acts determining the state policy in the field of education, there are no norms regulating the promotion and internationalization of research activities at higher education institutions.

The mentioned issues are regulated by internal acts of the university and certain regulations. (Websites: Tbilisi State Medical University; Georgian Technical University, (<https://tsmu.edu/ts>, n.d.) (<https://gtu.ge>, n.d.), 2023)

As the studied higher education institutions are authorized, the data provided in the internal documents of the university (available on the university websites) in terms of research and internationalization, correspond with the authorization standards. Namely, the promotion of the research is determined and the data are transparent. The funds for the financing of research are detailed in some cases. The talk is about grant projects (both – university-based and state-based or foreign).

Herewith, the system of evaluation and analysis of the productiveness of research activities of academic and scientific personnel, also, the mechanism for participation in the research process are developed at higher education institutions.

The internal university regulations of the higher education institutions existing both – in the capital and in regions, form the basis of the mentioned analysis.

In particular:

1. In Tbilisi - 7 state universities;
2. In regions - 3 state universities;
3. In Tbilisi - 9 private universities;
4. In regions - 2 private universities;
5. In Tbilisi - 4 teaching universities;
6. In regions - 3 teaching universities.

The research component, internationalization was the field of interest.

The mentioned data are mostly provided for in the strategic development plans of higher education institutions. The mechanisms for the university-based support of research activities, the organisational support structures, system of university-based funding of research events are established, informational support of the university-based research is provided, the events for the organisation and support of scientific research are held, general policy for the implementation of research, also, the system of assessment and analysis of the productivity of the scientific activities of academic and scientific personnel. (websites: Akaki Tsereteli State University; Batumi Shota Rustaveli State University; Tbilisi State Medical University, Tbilisi Technical University, (<https://www.at su.edu.ge>, n.d.) (<https://www.bs u.edu.ge>, n.d.) (<https://ts mu.edu/ts>, n.d.) (<https://gt u.ge>, n.d.), 2023)

The sources of funding of research activities at universities are:

- a) The funding allocated from the university budget for the development of research;
- b) The funding received under the university grant;
- c) The funding received from external sources.

The mentioned funding may be used for both – full funding and co-funding of the research project. The universities ensure the maintenance or increase of the budget established for projects for each consecutive year.

In order to increase the involvement of the university in international and local research projects, universities and their structural units take care of increasing the level of awareness of the academic personnel and researchers of the university regarding research projects and opportunities of participation in them, also informing the academic society on the achievements of the universities in terms of science and research.

The structural unit responsible for the development of research provides information on local and international research grants to the university personnel and students. Consultations are held for interested persons and they are provided with aid in terms of finding a desirable grant, the councils of development of scientific research are established.

After the research it was revealed that state universities, especially those existing in the capital, have more opportunities, which is reflected in the following:

1. The budget volume;
2. The number of research institutes;
3. The number of affiliate professors, researchers involved in the grants projects, promoting research, high index of productivity;
4. Mobility of students and the faculty.

For instance, throughout the last 10 years, more than 300 projects were implemented at one of the state universities of Tbilisi.

We see the difference in the direction of internationalization as well. For example, regarding one of the state universities of Tbilisi, apart from the fact that it is a member of numerous international organisations and associations, it is in partnership with more than 120 foreign universities, and under bilateral agreements and/or

joint international projects, more than 300 students, academic and administrative personnel participate in the short-term and long-term mobility programs. (websites: Tbilisi State Medical University, (<https://ts mu.edu/ts>, n.d.) (<https://gt u.ge>, n.d.), 2023). So-called private universities do not have such a great opportunity.

Herewith, more visits of foreign professors were performed at state universities, especially, in the capital, to read lectures or carry out other type of activities, provide consultations.

As for the university-based funding of research – it is known that respective units according to the educational program develop a budget, where funds are considered for various research activities (the data are mostly not available to the public).

However, in the internal university documentation of some higher education institutions, the sums determined for research are considered. The analysis shows that the funding of state universities, especially, those located in Tbilisi, is considerably higher in this regard. For instance, one of the state universities of the capital allocates more than 2 million Gel per year for the promotion of scientific studies, and in one of the state universities of the region, about 100 000 Gel is allocated for analogous purposes, and about 300 000 Gel in one of the private universities of Tbilisi.

Considering the budget and generally, the opportunities, universities, study universities fund the publication of handbooks, monographs, the printing and publication of scientific papers in high-rated journals both – in Georgia and abroad, they hold scientific conferences and finance the foreign business trips of affiliate personnel with the purpose of participation in conferences.

Research Methodology

Qualitative and quantitative studies were also conducted within the framework of the research, where the academic personnel of higher education institutions were determined as the target audience. The duration of interviews was 25-30 minutes. Private and public universities from regions and Tbilisi participated in the research.

During the qualitative study, the administrative personnel of higher education institutions were contacted, though, due to the overloaded work schedule, some of them refused to provide an in-depth interview.

The study was conducted in 8 universities out of the 62 higher education institutions of Georgia, and an in-depth interview was applied. The interviews were taken via the Zoom platform, via phone.

The quantitative study was conducted in June 2023 with the academic personnel employed at the higher education institutions existing in Georgia. Within the framework of the study, 141 respondents were selected on a random basis. The quantitative study questionnaire was prepared through Google Forms, and the information obtained through the study was processed via the SPSS program. The research aimed at studying the factors hindering the development of science and the evaluation of the challenges of research opportunities at higher education institutions of Georgia.

Within the framework of the study, the reports of the authorisation board of eleven universities were studied in relation to the 6th standard (research, development and/or other creative activities). It is noteworthy that the authorisation visits were performed and the conclusions were prepared between 2018-2021. (Conclusions of authorization experts, 2018-2021).

The mentioned standard consists of three subparagraphs: 6.2 – research activities; 6.2 – promoting research and internationalisation; 6.3 – evaluation of the research activities.

➤ *Higher education institution, considering its type and specifics of the field, performs research and creative activities;*

➤ *Ensures the efficiency of the doctoral thesis supervisors;*

➤ *The institution has transparent and fair procedures in terms of the evaluation and defence of dissertations, which correspond to specific fields;*

➤ *The universities have presented statements on research activities in the strategic document according to the standard.*

Interpretation of the results of the studied authorization reports, interviews and quantitative research results

➤ The study has shown that often the universities do not determine research priorities in their strategic documents, and when they determine it, it does not coincide with the studies conducted by their academic personnel;

➤ Memoranda executed by higher education institutions with foreign universities often bear formal character and there is no active cooperation;

➤ Higher education institutions do not have internal evaluation systems for research results and the factual indicators of ethical research;

➤ The reports on the evaluation of the outcomes of the activities of academic personnel, also, their analyses are not publicly available in order to ensure openness and transparency;

➤ The advantages of public universities in the direction of research must be noted due to the following circumstances: as a result of the implemented reform, after the accession of research institutes to state public universities, they have proceeded in this direction. However, this merger is often formal. It must be noted that higher education and research is not integrated in these terms. Namely, research institutes still work independently. Nevertheless, in the process of authorisation, of course, the activities of the mentioned research universities are regarded as the development of public universities in the direction of research activities. In terms of integration of education and research, there is a deficit of cooperation between higher education institutions and research institutes.

➤ There is no unified data system at higher education institutions, where it would be simple to find information on research institutes, authors of articles and other important data related to research;

➤ The participation of master's and doctoral students in the research projects is low;

➤ The practice of publication of papers of master's students, doctoral students and particularly, scholars in indexed journals (e.g., Scopus, Web of Science, ERIH PLUS and others) is low.

➤ It is noteworthy that in private universities, unlike public universities, the academic personnel receive payment only for lecture workloads and in terms of research activities, the costs related to the publication of research papers, their presentation at the conference and costs related to other related activities. However, in private universities, there is no practice of hourly payment allocated for research. In public universities, separate workload and payment is established. Therefore, there is a minimum margin of lecture workloads and the remaining time from the total workload must be used for research activities. There are also bonuses issued at public institutions not only for publishing a paper and participating in other research activities, but also for scientific activities.

Conclusion

As a result of the qualitative and quantitative studies conducted at the higher education institutions of Georgia the following questions were answered:

1. To what extent do the regulations existing in the country express the declared state policy?

It must be noted that there are ambiguous regulations in the legal acts determining the state policy in the field of education in terms of promoting research activities at higher education institutions.

As the studied higher education institutions are authorized, the data provided in the internal university documents (available on the university website) in terms of research and internationalization, correspond with the authorization standards. Namely, the promotion of research is determined and the data are transparent. Not always, but in some cases the sums for funding the studies are detailed. The talk is about grant projects (both – university-based and state-based or foreign).

The system of evaluation and analysis of the productiveness of the activities of academic and scholarly personnel is created and functions at higher education institutions, also, the mechanisms for promoting participation in the research process.

The university-based mechanisms for supporting research activities, the structures of organisational support of research activities, the system of the university-based funding of research events are created, informational support of university-based studies is provided, the events for the organisation and support of scientific research are held, general policy for the implementation of research, also, the system of evaluation and analysis of the productiveness of research activities of the scientific personnel is developed.

After the research it was revealed that state universities, especially those, existing in the capital, have more opportunities, which is expressed in the following:

- ✓ The budget volume;
- ✓ The number of research institutes;
- ✓ The number of affiliate professors, researchers involved in the grant projects, promoting research, high index of productivity;
- ✓ The mobility of students and the faculty.

As for the university-based funding of studies – it is known that the faculties develop budgets according to the educational program, which includes the funds for various scientific activities (the data are not available to the public).

However, in the university-based documents of certain higher education institutions, the funds determined for studies are included. The analysis shows that in these terms, the funding of state universities, particularly, those located in Tbilisi, is a lot higher. For example, Tbilisi State University allocates more than 2 million Gel annually for promoting research, while in one of the state universities of the region, about 100 000 Gel is allocated for analogous purposes, and about 300 000 Gel in one of the private universities of Tbilisi.

Considering the budget and generally, the opportunities, universities, study universities fund the publication of handbooks, monographs, the printing and publication of scientific papers in high-rated journals both – in Georgia and abroad, they hold scientific conferences and finance the foreign business trips of affiliate personnel with the purpose of participation in conferences.

2. What is the existing potential in the field of higher education and what are the main challenges faced by Georgian scholars?

In terms of human resources, the research has revealed the deficit of qualified scholars and experienced academic personnel at higher education institutions of Georgia, which has negative influence on the quality of research outcomes and hinders the development of the research culture at higher education institutions. Herewith, the lack of experienced academic personnel, who would be able to mentor and supervise students for research, negatively affects the research capabilities of Georgian higher education institutions.

There is no unified data system at higher education institutions, where it would be simple to find information on research institutes, authors of articles and other important data related to research;

The participation of master's and doctoral students in the research projects is low;

The practice of publication of papers of master's students, doctoral students and particularly, scholars in indexed journals (e.g., Scopus, Web of Science, ERIH PLUS and others) is low.

Lack of funding: one of the main challenges named by respondents is the lack of funding of research activities. Many institutes care about supporting research projects in order to ensure sufficient financial resources, buy the necessary equipment and promote research among faculty members.

First of all, limited funding and other resources prevent the development of research activities in Georgia.

Also, the research confirms that the universities have financial encouragement mechanisms for affiliate personnel, though, this sum is obtained only after the publication of a completed project/article.

Most of the respondents note that in private higher education institutions, unlike public universities, only the contact hours with students are funded and the

hourly remuneration for research/scientific activities is not determined.

It is noteworthy that in private universities, unlike public universities, the academic personnel receive payment only for lecture workloads and in terms of research activities, the costs related to the publication of research papers, their presentation at the conference and costs related to other related activities. However, in private universities, there is no practice of hourly payment allocated for research. In public universities, separate workload and payment is established. Therefore, there is a minimum margin of lecture workloads and the remaining time from the total workload must be used for research activities. There are also bonuses issued at public institutions not only for publishing a paper and participating in other research activities, but also for scientific activities (which coincides with the results of the quantitative research as well).

Infrastructure: the participants also noted that at higher education institutions the infrastructure also hinders the research capacities. Insufficient laboratory facilities, outdated technologies and limited access to the research databases hinder the ability of scientists to conduct high-quality research, participate in international conferences, cooperate with foreign scientists.

Limited cooperation: there is a lack of cooperation between researchers both – at institutes and beyond them. This limits the sharing of knowledge and resources, hinders the joint research opportunities of the institutes.

There is a lack of such structural units at universities, which would help the personnel with writing and proposing grant projects. There is a lack of competence in this direction.

The reports on the evaluation of the outcomes of the activities of academic personnel, also, their analyses are not publicly available in order to ensure openness and transparency;

The advantages of public universities in the direction of research must be noted due to the following circumstances: as a result of the implemented reform, after the accession of research institutes to state public universities, they have proceeded in this direction. Though, this merger is often formal. It must be noted that higher education and research are not integrated in these terms. Namely, research institutes still work independently. Nevertheless, in the process of authorisation, of course, the activities of the mentioned research universities are regarded as the development of public universities in the direction of research activities. In terms of integration of education and research, there is a deficit of cooperation between higher education institutions and research institutes.

Low motivation and recognition: the respondents underlined that the lack of recognition and motivation negatively affects the research capabilities. The non-existence of the merit-based system and limited career advancement based on research results in reduced motivation and devotion among researchers.

There are no support mechanisms, which would encourage academic personnel to participate in grants and project research programs.

Age: both – desk and quantitative studies confirm that the age of scientific/academic personnel is a challenge for today's higher education institutions. The respondents note that there are no proper pension supplements and it is very rare to be elected as an Emeritus. For example, the average age of the faculty members of various universities is 65. The attraction of young personnel still remains a problem. In frequent cases, universities have not determined a policy on how they are going to attract and retain young personnel.

Language barrier: most of the respondents note that those, who do not know the English language, face significant challenge in research activities. The researchers, who use English as a language of communication are more actively involved in international research and often publish articles in the journals with impact factor together with foreign co-authors. By overcoming the language barrier, the researchers will have the opportunity to participate in international grants competitions, in its turn, this will promote the internationalisation of research. There are cases, when a group of experts underlines a good index of internationalisation of a university, though, it also notes that "Much is left for the improvement of the knowledge of English among the academic personnel, to promote the research opportunities and integration in the international research environment".

Recommendations in terms of reinforcement of the academic personnel competence:

- Academic personnel should be given more opportunities and support in order to make grants and project proposals;
- It is also important to have open and transparent reports on the evaluation of the research outcomes in terms of academic personnel every year; also, to analyse the evaluation of the research results on academic personnel;
- It would be good to develop more complex approaches towards the evaluation of research considering the work of research institutes and other units. Herewith, it is important for the universities to elaborate and implement a system of monitoring and ensuring the research quality, which can also be seen as an authorisation and/or accreditation standard from the state in the future;
- In order to ensure the publicity and transparency of processes it is also important to have a unified data system, where it will be easy to find information and other important data regarding scientific institutes, authors of articles, in order to create a research profile of each institution and/or the units existing within it;
- It is important for the universities to determine the indicators of the performed work, such as the number of research papers and other publications in the internationally peer-reviewed journals, expected by it from each faculty and research centre annually and use other existing measures as well, in order to find out the area, where more attention must be paid for improvement purposes. Therefore, the work of all affiliate and invited personnel and, therefore, the faculty, may be evaluated;
- It would be good if the academic personnel

had certain support in terms of learning a foreign language, as most of the respondents mention that lack of language proficiency is an important challenge in research activities;

- As the attraction of young personnel remains a problem, it is important to develop respective approaches on how they are going to attract and retain young personnel;
- It is noteworthy and private universities should share the experience of some public universities. In particular, the determination of an hourly workload for research activities and respective remuneration. In practice, there is also additional remuneration for participating in various research activities;
- It is important to increase the funding for scientists. In the case of effective spending, it is feasible to enrich universities with research equipment and ensure the professional development of academic personnel, which, in its turn, would promote the development of research.
- It is also important to broaden the research field at higher education institutions, integrate teaching and science, also, diversify it, which will ensure the improvement of scientific results of the institution in the future;
- It is important for an educational institution to care for the development of an individual researcher and his/her career, which implies the promotion of mobility by higher education institutions, attraction of funding supporting innovative activities;
- It is necessary for an educational institution to ensure collaboration with similar institutions at the global level, which will become the grounds for the opportunities of inclusion in international research and determine the necessity to participate in target events on international innovative networks;
- Educational institutions must promote the international research cooperation of researchers by identifying big and complex challenges, determining the research profile of the institution and supporting the inclusion of the research in respective research groups;
- Higher institutions should revise the approaches to the employment of researchers, promote the global-scale employment of researchers and offer them a lifelong contract.

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